

THE EFFECT OF ACTUATING THE BASS TROMBONE SECOND VALVE ON THE QUALITY OF NOTE TRANSITION IN LEGATO

Renato Lisboa

CEGeME – Center for Research on Gesture and Music Expression, Federal University of Minas Gerais, Brazil

renatrom-
bone@gmail.com

Gustavo Machado

gustavomach-
oli@gmail.com

Thiago Campolina

thicampo-
lina@gmail.com

Mauricio Loureiro

mauricio.alves.lou-
reiro@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The independent activation of the two valves of the modern trombone, implemented in the 1950s, made it possible to play the same note by multiple positions. The innovation facilitated not only the execution of chromatic passages but also note transitions that involve slide displacement between positions far apart. The full range of possibilities allowed by this improvement is not yet widespread among trombonists. This paper discusses the effect of using the second valve of the bass trombone on the execution of legato note articulation. Note transitions produced in positions far apart were extracted from performances of orchestral excerpts. Expert musicians with professional experience in symphony orchestras were asked to use different valve configurations in the performances of two orchestral excerpts. Two descriptors were used to infer the quality of the transitions: (i) the time interval spent in carrying out the transitions (Transition Duration); and (ii) the energy stability during the transition (Energy Index). We verified an increase in efficiency in the articulation between these notes, played in legato when the second valve was used alone, by the statistically significant decrease of Transition Duration in 39.2% and increase of the Energy Index in 10.6% (both $df = 107$ and $p < 0.001$).

1. INTRODUCTION

The bass trombone is one of the most recent instruments that came to integrate into the modern symphony orchestra. The *Concerto for Orchestra Sz. 116*, a five-movement orchestral work composed by Béla Bartók in 1943, motivated trombone makers to search for mechanisms that would enable trombonists to produce a note Bartók wrote in that score for bass trombone, but until then not possible to play. With this innovation followed by further additions to the trombone, a new instrument was created, the bass trombone. Along with the development of this new instrument, new performance techniques were necessary for exploring, understanding, and dominating the new possibilities offered by this new instrument. Such techniques are still being developed by trombonists and instructors specialized in bass trombone. The great majority of trombonists play only on the tenor trombone, thus ignoring the countless performance possibilities that may be achieved

with the use of the bass trombone valves, whether combined or independently, as stated by Thomas on a study on the use of valves in the Bass Trombone [1]. The author addresses some criteria for choosing the use of valves and slide positions for better and easier interpretation which include tempo, articulation, and proximity between slide positions.

Due to several demands for producing new lower notes on the bass trombone, a second valve, the Gb valve, was added to the first valve, the F valve, of the early bass trombone¹. On the early double-valve bass trombone models, the operation of both valves was not independent, i.e., the F valve needed to be triggered to trigger the Gb valve. Modern bass trombone constructions allow the independent operation of each valve, a resource that offers four distinct tunings in a single instrument: Bb, F, Gb, and D. Figure 1 shows a Holton TR 181 bass trombone equipped with two independent valves.

Figure 1. Bass trombone, Model Holton TR 181, with two independent valves.

The development of the second valve initially sought to facilitate the execution of chromatic passages, but the independent operation of each valve made it possible the production of a note by multiple positions, which in turn facilitated the execution of note transitions that involve slide displacement between positions far apart.

1.1 The legato on the trombone

The note articulation in legato is one of the most difficult technical aspects for the trombonist. Most modern brass instruments provide valves for modifying the tube length to alter the pitch. Mechanisms, such as the valves or pistons, facilitate fast pitch changes, which is required for legato note articulation. Instead of the valves, the tube length

¹ The F and Gb valves open additional tube paths, augmenting the tube length for lowering the fundamental tuning, which in turn, also makes it possible to obtain additional harmonic series

of the trombone is modified gradually by a telescoping slide, a mechanism that has remained largely the same since the 15th century, which confers the instrument a unique characteristic of gradual pitch change while the slide is displaced. Such characteristic presents a major problem for trombonists for legato articulation, which is only achieved by subtle tongue articulation, to better connect one note to another without producing continuous pitch change during the note transition. The fundamental technique of legato involves the tongue partially obstructing the airflow into the instrument's mouthpiece as the slide is moved from one position to another, muffling the sound emission during the slide trajectory.

This study aims at verifying to what extent the use of the second valve of the bass trombone may improve the execution of legato articulation between specific notes. The technique of using the second valve alone has only been addressed in more recent bass trombone methods since the last decade, after bass trombone teachers became aware of this demand. Most bass trombonists have used the second valve only for playing four notes in the lowest register, thus disregarding a whole range of possibilities that the independent use of the valves may offer. Galloway [2] states that, just as tenor trombonists do not make adequate use of the F valve, the bass trombonist needs to actively accept the possibilities of the second independent Gb valve. The author quotes the renowned trombone teacher and author of several methods Alan Raph: "I regret that nobody ever plays the second valve alone, which is equivalent to driving a half-empty bus all the time".

It is expected that the results of this investigation may present a valuable contribution to bass trombone players and instructors, as well for composers for better exploring the possibilities of this instrument in solo, chamber music, and symphonic repertoire.

2. METHODS

2.1 Experiment

2.1.1 Musical Material

Several excerpts extracted from the symphony orchestra repertoire for bass trombone containing specific note transitions matching the purpose of this study were selected. This paper brings analyzes carried out on two excerpts extracted from Anton Bruckner's the first movement (*Allegro*) of Symphony No. 5 in B flat Major WAB 105, shown in Figure 2. Each excerpt contains three note transitions in legato (marked with arrows) presenting appropriate characteristics for the proposed analysis. Note transitions will be referred to as T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, and T6.

2.1.2 Experiment Procedure

Three bass trombone professional players with proven symphony orchestra experience were recruited to perform the excerpts for the experiment. Two conditions of configuration for valve use were established: **condition 1** - basic trombone positions without using the second valve; **condition 2** - using the second valve alone. Participants were asked to execute both excerpts six consecutive times in each of the two conditions, respecting strictly the legato

indication on the score. The total of 36 executions were captured by an Audio Technica ATM 350u microphone (Pro 35), attached to the instrument trombone bell and a Mixer/Interface Yamaha MG10-XU 24bits 192khz equipped with Pro Tools HD 12.5.0 Software.

Figure 2. Orchestral excerpts for bass trombone from the 1st movement of Symphony No. 5 in B flat Major WAB 105 by Anton Bruckner, c. 271 (a) and 286 (b). Note transitions considered for analysis are marked with arrows.

Figure 3 provides a graphical representation of the trajectories of the trombone slide for the six analyzed note transitions for **condition 1** (left panel) and **condition 2** (right panel). Colors indicate valves use: basic trombone positions without using a valve (black); using the first valve (grey); using the second valve alone (unfilled).

Figure 3. Trajectories of the trombone slide for the six analyzed note transitions

2.1.3 Audio segmentation

The audio recorded in the experiment was firstly segmented into notes, by detecting note onsets on the average energy curve, using the EXPAN system developed in the CEGeME² laboratory of UFMG [3] and the Sonic Visualizer software.

The analysis proposed in this study is focused on the transition region between the considered notes, which is delimited by the beginning of the decay of the first note and the end of attack of the subsequent note. The beginning of decay is the instant of the most accentuated drop in amplitude close to the end of the note, while the end of attack is the instant of maximum amplitude close to the beginning of the note. These instants were estimated using the Sonic Visualizer software by manual annotation on the average energy curve, which describes with good approximation how we perceive sound intensity. Due to the high degree of transient content in the transition region between the notes, where the spectral content is unstable and noisy, plotting the spectral flux³ over the RMS curve on the SonicVisualizer, offered additional information for estimating these two instants.

2.1.4 Parametrization

Two descriptors were used to infer the quality of the legato transitions: (i) the time interval spent in carrying out the transitions (*Transition Duration*); and (ii) an index for measuring the energy stability during the transition (*Energy Index*). The *Transition Duration* was defined by the two instants, beginning of decay and end of attack, obtained by subtracting the instant of beginning of decay of the first note from the instant of end attack of the subsequent note. The *Energy Index*, EI was defined as suggested by Maestre [4], based on a hypothetically ideal legato transition between two notes without any decrease in energy, represented by the straight line L , defined by the instants of beginning of decay of the first note and the end of attack of the subsequent note. It is obtained by the ratio between the area A_1 comprised between line L and the RMS curve in the transition region and the total area $A_1 + A_2$ below line L , as presented by Equation 1 and Figure 4. Its value is less than or equal to 1, being close to 1 for an “ideally” legato transition.

$$EI = 1 - \left[\frac{\sum_{release_i}^{attack_{i+1}} L(t) + RMS(t)}{\sum_{release_i}^{attack_{i+1}} L(t)} \right] \quad (1)$$

Figure 4 – Energy Index for the transition between two notes

3. RESULTS

Figures 5 and 7 show the boxplot of both descriptors, Transition Duration and Energy Index, for each factor, transition (a), participant (b), valve condition (c), and take (d), of which transition, participant and take are unwanted factors. Figures 6 and 8 plot the means with the 95 % confidence interval of both descriptors for each factor.

Figure 5 – Boxplots of Transition Duration for factors transition (a), participant (b), valve condition (c), and take (d).

Figure 6 – Means and confidence interval of Transition Duration for factors transition (a), participant (b), valve condition (c), and take (d).

² CEGeME – Center for Research on Gesture and Musical Expression, Federal University of Minas Gerais – UFMG.

³ Spectral flux measures the spectral change between two successive frames and is computed as the squared difference between the normalized magnitudes of the spectra of two successive short-term windows.

Figure 7: Boxplots of Energy Index for factors transition (a), participant (b), valve condition (c), and take (d).

Figure 8: Means and confidence interval of Energy Index for factors transition (a), participant (b), valve condition (c), and take (d).

A Linear Model was used to estimate the effects of factors, valve condition, transition, participant and take on the Transition Duration, as well as on Energy Index. A log transformation was applied to meet assumptions of normality for the residuals, verified by Shapiro-Wilk test ($W = 0.991$, $p = 0.173$ for Transition Duration and $W = 0.992$, $p = 0.305$ for Energy Index). Table 1 presents the effects of each level of each factor with their respective p-values. Estimates shown in Table 1 correspond to back transformation resulting in geometric means ratios.

A paired t-test was used to evaluate the isolated effect of the valve condition on Transition Duration and Energy Index. Normality of the paired differences was verified by Shapiro-Wilk test ($W = 0.974$, $p > 0.01$ for Transition Duration and $W = 0.990$, $p > 0.01$ for Energy Index). The test showed that the effect of condition 2 on the Transition Duration was of a significant decrease of 38 ms (32 - 45 of 95% of CI; $df = 107$; $p < 0.001$), from 98 ms to 60 ms (39.2%), with *Cohen's d* effect size of 1.21. The effect on

the Energy Index was of a significant increase of 0.07 (.09 - 0.04 of 95% of CI; $df = 107$; $p < 0.001$), from 0.59 to 0.66 (10.6%), with *Cohen's d* effect size of 0.53.

Predictors	Transition Duration		Energy Index	
	Estimates	<i>p</i>	Estimates	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	132.10	<0.001	0.54	<0.001
Cond [C2]	0.61	<0.001	1.11	<0.001
Tran [T2]	0.82	0.001	1.03	0.351
Tran [T3]	0.75	<0.001	1.18	<0.001
Tran [T4]	1.06	0.288	1.02	0.422
Tran [T5]	0.76	<0.001	1.08	0.007
Tran [T6]	0.79	<0.001	1.21	<0.001
Name [TB]	0.90	0.009	1.02	0.250
Name [TC]	0.85	<0.001	1.09	<0.001
Take [2]	0.97	0.625	1.06	0.037
Take [3]	0.90	0.062	1.07	0.015
Take [4]	0.88	0.028	1.10	0.001
Take [5]	0.86	0.009	1.10	0.001
Take [6]	0.85	0.003	1.05	0.087
Observations	216		216	
df	202		202	
$R^2 / R^2_{\text{adjusted}}$	0.619 / 0.595		0.443 / 0.407	

Table 1: Effects of factors, valve condition, transition, participant, and take with their respective p-values, estimated by a linear model with log transformed data (estimates correspond to geometric means ratios).

4. DISCUSSION

The execution of note transitions **T1**, **T2**, **T3**, **T4**, and **T5**, in Condition 1, when the trombonist was instructed not to use the second valve, required the slide position change from the first to the fifth positions, demanding a range of movement of the arm of ca. 38 cm, while in transition **T6** the slide position change was from the third to the first positions, demanding a movement of the arm of a range ca. 20 cm. Along with the slide trajectory, tongue articulation was necessary for muffling eventual continuous pitch variation (small glissando). Results indicated the efficiency of the use of the second valve alone, Condition 2, in all six transitions, when compared to Condition 1. Transition efficiency was inferred by the time interval spent for executing the transition, as well as by the estimate of energy continuation measured by the descriptor Energy Index as defined above. The effect of Condition 2 on the transition duration was high, while on the energy continuation was medium.

Condition 2, in transitions **T1**, **T2**, **T4**, and **T5** required a simple actuation of the second valve, and in transition **T3** an alternation, releasing the first valve to trigger the second one. Transition **T6** in Condition 2 required the slide

position change from the third to the first positions, demanding a range of movement of the arm of ca. 17 cm, associated with the actuation of the second valve.

The participants answered a questionnaire for reporting their observations on each of the excerpts. The first two transitions were considered easier to perform with the second valve and with a more pleasant sound without much effort. Regarding transition **T3**, the difficulties pointed out by the participants concerned the exact timing of the activation of the second valve, with the risk of breaking the legato or going out of tune, since the production of this note involves higher harmonics, which requires fine-tuning correction by lowering the slide lightly.

Even though the reported hardship for executing transition **T3** in condition 2, results indicated that better quality of legato in all transitions was achieved, according to both descriptors adopted in this study to approach legato quality. Moreover, the benefit introduced by the use of the second valve to execute all transitions, including transitions **T3** and **T6** was unanimously reported. One participant reported that he felt an economy in the air column to complete the sentence in one breath. One participant reported difficulty executing transition **T6** in Condition 2, due to the slide position change being contrary to the pitch change. However, the others participants reported that this movement facilitated the execution of this transition, helping to maintain the air column and thus avoid continuous pitch variation.

5. CONCLUSION

This work addresses the use of the second valve in the bass trombone, bringing to light the potential that different possibilities of using this valve may improve the performance of this instrument. This is an opportune approach, given the widespread lack of knowledge of the many possible uses of this valve, which can be explained by the fact that the state of development that the bass trombone valves currently reached is quite recent, in particular the resource of triggering the valves independently.

In addition to the excerpt presented in this study, other musical excerpts are being analyzed to generalize the evidence of the effect of using adequately the bass trombone valves in legato transitions. Observed and reported undesirable intensity accents, timbre quality worsens and to what extent the presence of eventual short glissando was avoided has still to be verified in future analysis.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] Thomas, Casey Winn. "Valve technique for the independent double-valve bass trombone: a pedagogical review and method". Graduate College of The University of Iowa, EUA, 2015.
- [2] Galloway, David J. "A response from South Africa". *International Trombone Association Journal*, Vol. XII, No. 3, 1984, p. 22.
- [3] Campolina, T. A. M., Mota, D. A., & Loureiro, M. A. "Expan: A tool for musical expressiveness analysis". In *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference of Students of Systematic Musicology - SYSMUS*, 2009, pp. 24–27.
- [4] Maestre, E., Gómez, E. "Automatic characterization of dynamics and articulation of expressive monophonic recordings". In: *CITeseer*. In *Proceedings of the 118th Audio Engineering Society Convention*. [S.l.], 2005